

ISic0801

Fragment of a public Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

honorific; building (?)

Material

marble (white)

Object

tabula

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated 9 September 1970, near entrance to room 2 of west portico of
the agora

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20224

Physical Description

Fragment of white marble slab, broken on all sides; finished on the reverse

Dimensions

Height 26 cm

Width 22 cm

Depth 2.5 cm

Layout

Parts of two lines of latin letters are preserved. Substantial vacat below line 2.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are neatly V-cut, of wide proportions, with minimal serifs. P is open; S

has a larger upper half, leaning slightly to the right. Words are separated by a comma-like three pointed serif.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 38-40 mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. [---]CILIV[---]

2. [---]R · S · P · INQ[---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

It is not possible to know what the likely extent of the stone was, either to the left and right, or above and below the surviving text. The letters of line 1 are most likely to be part of a name: Caecilius and Acilius are the most common, but a number of other names of this form such as Lucilius, Maecilius, Otacilius, Pacilius, Precilius, and Racilius are also attested. Both Caecilius (ISic0803 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0803>] ; RPC I, 628-629; Cic. Verr. 2.2.23) and Acilius (ISic0804 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0804>]) are attested at Halaesa. The abbreviation in line 2 is most easily resolved as *restituit sua pecunia* ("restored (x) at his own expense"), although this cannot be certain, and Scibona's suggestion of *inopia* for the word that follows is certainly plausible (i.e. that the individual named in the first part of the inscription restored something – a building perhaps – at his/her own expense due to the lack of funds on the part of the town or another body or individual). Manganaro's suggestion of *incohavit* is also possible, and there are few other alternatives beginning INC or INO.

Digital identifiers:

TM 175719

EDR 075541

EDCS 9401425

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0801>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4021529

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0801. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4339504>

Photo J. Prag